

CARDIAC MANIFESTATIONS OF ANKYLOSING SPONDYLITIS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction and Objective : This study aimed to carry out a literature review on the cardiac manifestations of ankylosing spondylitis (AS). **Methods** : A bibliographic survey was carried out between 2011 and 2021, in the PUBMED and SciELO databases. The descriptors were used: Spondyloarthritis, Ankylosing Spondylitis, Cardiac manifestations, and Cardiovascular

manifestations, resulting in 21 studies, after reading the abstracts, only 13 were selected, which addressed the cardiac involvement of the disease. **Results** : The literature points out that due to its inflammatory pattern and chronification, extra-articular manifestations can be observed in some patients with AS. In these outcomes, it is worth noting cardiac conduction disorders. The incidence of cardiovascular involvement in patients with AS is more commonly reported in 10-30% of these individuals with the disease. Valve involvement is present, the most reported aortic, with greater sensitivity and specificity for AS. Such involvements cannot be monitored only by inflammatory tests, such as erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) and c-reactive protein (CRP), since there is no uniform character in the evolution of AS and its extra-articular conditions. **Conclusion** : The extra-articular manifestations in AS, although rare, are indicative of a worse prognosis for patients with carriers and, consequently, present high morbidity, therefore, they should be diagnosed and treated early to increase the chances of a better prognosis for these individuals.

Keywords: Ankylosing Spondylitis. Cardiovascular diseases. HLA-B27 antigen.

INTRODUCTION

Ankylosing spondylitis (AS) is a chronic autoimmune rheumatological disease that mainly affects the axial skeleton. This condition has a genetic relationship with the HLA-B27 gene, which is present in around 80% of AS cases, but the presence of the gene does not necessarily indicate the onset of the disease. Although AS most commonly affects the axial joints, there are reports in the literature about the chances of extra-articular involvement, especially cardiac manifestations which, even with a low incidence, have a great influence on the patient's prognosis and management.

METHODOLOGY

Articles were searched in the PUBMED and SciELO databases, using the descriptors: Spondyloarthritis, Ankylosing Spondylitis, Cardiac manifestations and Cardiovascular manifestations, resulting in 21 studies. After selecting only articles that addressed cardiac disorders, 13 were eligible for the development of the work.

RESULTS

Ankylosing spondylitis is characterized by being an inflammatory and immune-mediated disease, which mainly affects the joints of the axial skeleton. Due to its inflammatory and chronic pattern, extra-articular manifestations can be observed in some patients with AS.

Among the manifestations that do not affect the patient's axial spine, cardiac involvement stands out mainly. In these outcomes, it is important to observe cardiac conduction disorders. In diseases of aortic origin, such as aortic regurgitation and aortitis, it is noted that the most important valve abnormalities described in AS are thickening and dilation of the aortic root, thickening and retraction of the aortic cusp, aortic and mitral regurgitation in addition to diastolic dysfunction of the left ventricle. . The incidence of cardiovascular involvement in patients with AS is most commonly reported in 10-30% of these individuals, with male sex and obesity as risk factors. Valvular involvement is present, the most reported being aortic, with greater sensitivity and specificity for AS. Such disorders cannot be monitored solely by inflammatory tests, such as erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) and c-reactive protein (CRP), as there is no uniformity in the evolution of AS and its extra-articular conditions.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Extra-articular manifestations in AS, although rare, are indicative of a worse prognosis for patients with AS and consequently present high morbidity, and should therefore be diagnosed and treated early to increase the chances of a better prognosis for these individuals. Therefore, the present study analyzed the main causes of extra-axial involvement in AS, focusing on the cardiac site, in order to highlight the most common cardiovascular disorders reported in the literature and, therefore, seek to guarantee a better prognosis in the search for reducing morbidity and mortality. in this population by improving diagnostic methods and treatment protocols.

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